

Primary tillers of 60-d-seedlings produced panicles in 21 d after transplanting, irrespective of N level, but there were only 2-3 tillers/hill.

Increasing N increased dry matter production, grain yield, and tillering at both seedling ages (see table).

At 200 kg N/ha, 60-d seedlings yielded grain on par with that at 150 kg N in 40-d seedlings. At 100+25+25 kg N, 60-d seedlings yielded on par with 40d seedlings at 50+25+25 kg N. Daily production increased with N application at a declining rate.

Main field duration of older seedlings was affected by N level, but there was no significant difference in field duration between seedling ages at higher N levels. The 40-d seedlings yielded better with less N. □

Impact of different soil moisture status on transplanted aman varieties

M. J. Islam, K. A. Haq, M. S. Rahman, and M. B. Rahman, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

We studied the effect of soil moisture status on rice yield in 1983 transplanted aman at BRRI. Soil moisture status was monitored in farmer fields from panicle initiation to crop maturity and 112 5-m² crop-cuts were collected from fields with different moisture status. Varietal reaction and grain yield, adjusted to 14% moisture content, were recorded,

With continuous standing water, BR11 yielded highest, 6.2 t/ha, which was 210% higher than yield with visible desiccation.

Yield of transplanted aman cultivars at different soil moisture levels, Gazipur, Bangladesh.^a

Soil moisture status	Average yield ^b (t/ha)								
	BR11 14	BR10 3	BR4 8	Pajam 30	Nizersail 23	Chandra sail 16	Chini- gura ⁹ 6	Kaligira 6	Binni 3
5-6 cm standing water	6.2 (210)	-	-	4.1 (128)	-	-	2.8 (47)	-	-
Saturated	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Moist but not saturated	4.9 (145)	-	3.6 (33)	3.5 (94)	-	-	-	-	-
Hair-like cracks	3.9 (95)	4.6 (31)	-	2.8 (56)	2.4 (50)	2.9 (61)	2.6 (36)	1.9 (28)	-
Visible cracks	-	-	3.0 (11)	2.6 (44)	2.2 (38)	2.3 (28)	-	-	-
Visible desiccation	2.0	3.5	2.7	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.9	1.5	1.2
Av	3.9	3.9	3.2	2.8	1.8	2.2	2.3	1.7	1.2

^aFigures under each variety name indicate the number of samples. Values in parentheses in each column indicate percent yield increase over the yield with visible desiccation.

BR10 and BR11 yielded an average 3.9 t/ha (see table). BR10 and BR11 were more sensitive to water stress than Pajam.

Of the local varieties, Chinigura yielded highest with an average 2.3 t/ha. □

Isozymes, possible markers for blue-green algae (BGA) identification

J. C. Glaszmann, Ingenieur de Recherches, IRAT, visiting associate scientist, and P. A. Roger, Maitre de Recherches, ORSTOM, and visiting scientist, IRR1

To evaluate the potential of electrophoretically detectable isozymes for identifying BGA strains, especially in soil inoculation experiments, we worked to develop a sample preparation method that maximizes zymograms consistency.

The technique is horizontal starch gel electrophoresis using 14% starch in a tris (0.034 M) histidine (0.018 M) gel buffer with pH 8.0 and a tris (0.400 M) citrate (0.105 M) electrode buffer with pH 8.0. Zymograms were revealed by standard specific histochemical staining.

In a preliminary survey, 4 of 18 enzymes were observed in most of the tested strains (20 species in 9 genera) at different growth stages. They were phos-

1. Synthetic diagram of zymograms of various extracts of Anabaena PCC 7120. L = laboratory, P = phytotron, G = greenhouse, T = thawing, G = thawing + manual grinding, S = thawing + sonication.